

A Study on Numerical Analysis and Optimization and Applications in Machine Learning

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This report is dedicated to my
Respected Parents and Teachers

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Zakia Khanom Tisha

Certificate

This is to certify that the Zakia Khanom Tisha, bearing roll 160091 and registration no. 41636, have been completed her B.Sc. (Hons.) report entitled “**A Study on Numerical Analysis and Optimization and Applications in Machine Learning**” under my supervision and guidance in the Department of Mathematics, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342.

I wish her every success in life.

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Contents

Abstract.....	6
Chapter - 1.....	7
Introduction to Numerical Linear Algebra.....	7
Motivation to Numerical Linear Algebra	8
Interpolation Problem	8
Boundary Value Problem.....	9
Finite difference Method.....	10
Execution Time.....	12
Standard problems of equation.....	13
Introduction to Numerical Methods.....	14
Numerical Solution of System of linear Equation	14
Numerical methods for computing eigenvalues.....	14
Numerical Methods for Ordinary Differential Equations	15
Methods of solving IVPs.....	15
Methods of solving BVPs	15
Chapter – 2.....	16
Floating Point Arithmetic & Stability	16
Conditioning of System	16
Condition Number of a matrix:	17
Floating point number	18
Machine precision.....	19
IEEE 754 Floating Point Standard:.....	20
Stability of an algorithm	20
Chapter – 3.....	21
Iterative Methods for solving linear system.....	21
Fixed Point Iteration	23
Fixed point:	23
SOR method.....	24
Steepest-Descent Method for solving the system $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$	26
Conjugate Gradient Method for solving the system $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$	28
Chapter – 4.....	30
Numerical Methods for computing Eigenvalues	30

Eigenvalue Problem	30
Singular Value Decomposition	31
Algorithm of the Singular Value Decomposition	31
Power Method.....	32
Chapter – 5.....	34
Numerical Methods for Solving ODEs.....	34
Numerical Methods for IVPs.....	34
Single step method for solving IVPs.....	35
Multistep methods for solving IVPs.....	36
Chapter – 6.....	37
Machine learning	37
Correlation between machine learning and mathematics	37
Linear Algebra Concept in Machine Learning	37
Application of Numerical methods in Machine learning.....	38
Learning/Parameter Estimation.....	38
Inference	39
Numerical Integration	39
Numerical Linear Algebra	39
Finite Precision Arithmetic	40
Conclusion	41
References.....	42

Abstract

In computational mathematics, Numerical Analysis is an essential part to solve any numerical problem effectively when the problems are completely different from manually problem solving as computers need an effective approximation of an infinite number of solutions or data. As machine learning algorithms depend on the automation ability to apply complex mathematical calculations to big data faster than ever, numerical methods are a must to solve and approximate this kind of problem. This report is an overview of Numerical analysis and Optimization, the Methods of solving to achieve an effective result and application of numerical analysis in Machine learning problems. In a Data driven Model or simply a machine learning problem where analytic method may not exist, or analytic method is quite time consuming whether for huge data or due to complex function involved, numerical methods are crucial. In this report, there will be an insight of both numerical analysis and machine learning problems.

Chapter - 1

Introduction to Numerical Linear Algebra

Let $A \in R^{m \times n}$ be an $m \times n$ and let $b \in R^m$ be a vector. If the matrix A is very large as $10^6 \times 10^6$, then the approximate solution of $Ax = b$ that is $x \in R^n$ can't be solved with the help of computers. In devising algorithms for the numerical solution of such linear systems, we will exploit the properties of matrix A .

If the matrix $A \in R^{n \times n}$ is a square matrix, then we may want to find the eigenvalues λ and the corresponding eigenvectors $x \in R^n$, that is,

$$Ax = \lambda x$$

Linear algebra focused on the existence of the eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors. However, numerical linear algebra is concerned with the numerical computation of the eigenvalues on a computer for large square A . [1]

Motivation to Numerical Linear Algebra

Interpolation Problem

Let there be given N data sites $a \leq x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_N \leq b$ in $[a, b]$ and corresponding observations $f_1, f_2, \dots \in R$. But, if there is unknown function f such that $f(x_i) = f_i$, then the problem is called the interpolation problem.

To reconstruct the function that is unknown we have to choose a set of N continuous basis functions $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_N \in C([a, b])$ and to approximate f by a function s of the form

$$s(x) = \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_j \varphi_j(x),$$

Where the coefficients are determined by the interpolation conditions

$$f_i = s(x_i) = \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_j \varphi_j(x_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

Which constructs a linear system in an that can be written in Matrix form as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1(x_1) & \alpha_2(x_1) & \dots & \alpha_N(x_1) \\ \alpha_1(x_2) & \alpha_2(x_2) & \dots & \alpha_N(x_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \alpha_1(x_N) & \alpha_2(x_N) & \dots & \alpha_N(x_N) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_N \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \\ \vdots \\ f_N \end{pmatrix}$$

The matrix in the system is an $N \times N$ matrix. If N is too large, let $N \geq 10^6$, then such a linear system is not easy to solve. For a computer approximating such a huge linear system is hard. The solution finding and approximation method of this system will be discussed in the upcoming chapter. [2]

Boundary Value Problem

Let any differential equation for a function $u(x)$ which is twice continuously differentiable is

$$-\frac{d^2u(x)}{dx^2} + u(x) = f(x) \quad \text{on } (0,1) \dots\dots\dots (2.1)$$

Subject to boundary conditions

$$u(0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad u(1) = 0. \quad \dots\dots\dots (2.2)$$

The function f in equation (2.1) is continuous on $[0,1]$

This above problem is an example of a one-dimensional boundary value problem. If we want to solve this boundary value problem numerically, we can use finite differences. The main focus here is to approximate the derivative by difference quotients.

$$u'(x) \approx \frac{u(x+h) - u(x)}{h} \quad \text{or} \quad u'(x) \approx \frac{u(x) - u(x-h)}{h} \quad \dots\dots (2.3)$$

The above first formula is known as forward difference while the second equation is a backward difference. Using a forward difference and then backward rule for the second derivative leads to the centered second difference

$$\begin{aligned}
 u''(x) &\approx \frac{u'(x+h) - u'(x)}{h} \approx \frac{1}{h} \left(\frac{u(x+h) - u(x)}{h} - \frac{u(x) - u(x-h)}{h} \right) \\
 &= \frac{u(x+h) - 2u(x) + u(x-h)}{h^2} \dots\dots\dots (2.4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Finite difference Method

When finding a numerical approximation using finite differences, we divide the interval $[0,1]$ into $n + 1$ subintervals of equal length $h = \frac{1}{n + 1}$ with endpoints at the equally spaced nodes

$$x_i = ih = \frac{i}{(n + 1)}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n, n + 1,$$

We have to construct a vector $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}^h = (u_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, u_{n+1})^T$ such that u_j is an approximation of $u(x_j)$

Where $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, n+1$, where u is the exact solution to the boundary value problem.

Expressing (2.1) and (2.2) using $x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}$ and replacing the derivative using finite differences,

$$-\frac{u(x_{i+1}) - 2u(x_i) + u(x_{i-1}))}{h^2} + u(x_i) \approx f(x_i), \quad i=1,2,\dots,n \quad \dots\dots(2.5)$$

And

$$u(x_0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad u(x_{n+1}) = 0 \quad \dots\dots\dots(2.6)$$

Execution Time

Cost factors for the execution time of a program in numerical analysis include:

- floating point operations (i.e., the real arithmetic operations: +, −, ·, /, √)
- memory access
- overhead (unaccounted operations and memory access) In an ideal world, the floating-point operations (flop) would be the only cost factor of the execution time of a program and it would suffice to count them

Problem	Dimension	flop	flop (m = n = p)
$x'y$	$x, y \in R^m$	$2m$	$2m$
xy'	$x \in R^m, y \in R^n$	mn	m^2
Ax	$A \in R^{m \times n}, x \in R^n$	$2mn$	$2m^2$
AB	$A \in R^{m \times n}, B \in R^{n \times p}$	$2mnp$	$2m^3$

Standard problems of equation

Linear systems of equations:

Solve $Ax = b$. Here A is a given $n - by - n$ nonsingular real or complex matrix, & b is a given column vector with n entries, and x is a column vector with n entries that we wish to compute.

Least squares problems:

Compute the x that minimizes $\|Ax - b\|_2$. Here A is $m - by - n$, x is $m - by - 1$, b is $m - by - 1$, and $\|y\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_i |y_i|^2}$ is called the two-norm of the vector y . If $m > n$ so that we have more equations than unknowns, the system is called overdetermined. In this case we cannot generally solve $Ax = b$ exactly. If $m < n$, the system is called underdetermined, and we will have infinitely many solutions.

Eigenvalue problems:

Given an $n - by - n$ matrix A , find an $n - by - 1$ nonzero vector x and a scalar λ so that $Ax = \lambda x$.

Singular value problems:

Given an m -by- n matrix A , find an n -by-1 nonzero vector x and scalar λ so that $A^T A x = \lambda x$. We will see that this special kind of eigenvalue problem is important enough to merit separate consideration and algorithms [3]

Introduction to Numerical Methods

To solve different numerical problems mathematicians, use different methods. In this section we will give a short introduction to justify the statement. System of linear equation, IVP and BVP, Computing eigenvalues etc. are the most common numerical problems. There are many methods to find the efficient solutions. However, we will just discuss the most popular methods. Brief description will be discussed in later chapters. [1]

Numerical Solution of System of linear Equation

The most popular methods for solving system of linear equation are -

- a) Direct Methods
- b) Iterative Methods

Numerical methods for computing eigenvalues

In computational mathematics eigenvalues are the most important. The methods for computing eigenvalues are -

- a) Singular Value Decomposition
- b) Power Method
- c) Jacobi Method

Numerical Methods for Ordinary Differential Equations

The most interesting part of numerical analysis is to solve differential equations. During working on different fields, Ordinary differential equation solving plays a key role. In short, there are two types of ODEs problems: Initial Value Problems (IVPs) and Boundary Value Problems (BVPs)^[5]

Methods of solving IVPs

- a) Single step method
- b) Multi-Step Method

Methods of solving BVPs

- a) Shooting Method
- b) Finite Difference Method
- c) Collocation Method
- d) Galerkin Method

Chapter – 2

Floating Point Arithmetic & Stability

Conditioning of System

Well conditioning system

If small changes in data produce small changes in solution, then the system is called well-conditioned system

Ill-conditioned (badly conditioned) system

If small changes in system in the data can produce large changes in the solution, then the system is called ill conditioned system

Suppose we have a linear system $Ax = b$, where $A = (a_{ij})$ is in $C^{n \times n}$ or $R^{n \times n}$,
That is,

$$a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1$$

$$a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = b_2$$

.....

$$a_{n1}x_1 + a_{n2}x_2 + \dots + a_{nn}x_n = b_n$$

We perturb the system $Ax = b$ by $A + \Delta A$ and $b + \Delta b$ so that $x + \Delta x$ is a solution of the perturbed system $(A + \Delta A)(x + \Delta x) = (b + \Delta b)$

$$(A + \Delta A)(x + \Delta x) = (b + \Delta b) \Rightarrow (A + \Delta A)\Delta x + Ax = b + \Delta b - \Delta Ax$$

$$(A + \Delta A)\Delta x + Ax = b + \Delta b - \Delta Ax \Rightarrow (A + \Delta A)\Delta x = \Delta b - (\Delta A)x$$

Let us assume that $(A + \Delta A)$ is invertible so that $\Delta x = (A + \Delta A)^{-1}(\Delta b - (\Delta A)x)$, that is, $|\Delta x| \leq \|(A + \Delta A)^{-1}\| (|\Delta b| + |\Delta A| |x|)$

Which gives a first estimate on the absolute error $|\Delta x|$

However, more relevant is the relative error $\frac{|\Delta x|}{|x|}$

$$\frac{|\Delta x|}{|x|} \leq \|(A + \Delta A)^{-1}\| \frac{|\Delta b| + |\Delta A| |x|}{|x|}$$

$$\frac{|\Delta x|}{|x|} \leq \|(A + \Delta A)^{-1}\| |A| \frac{|\Delta b| + |\Delta A| |x|}{|A| |x|}$$

$$\frac{|\Delta x|}{|x|} \leq \|(A + \Delta A)^{-1}\| |A| \left(\frac{|\Delta b|}{|b|} + \frac{|\Delta A|}{|A|} \right)$$

The last estimate in the above equation shows that the relative input error magnified by a factor $\|(A + \Delta A)^{-1}\| |A|$ gives an upper bound for the relative output error. [6]

Condition Number of a matrix:

The condition number of an invertible square matrix A with respect to induced or compatible matrix norm $\|\cdot\|$ is defined as

$$\kappa(A) = \|A\| \|A^{-1}\|$$

Floating point number

In everyday life we use decimal representation of numbers. For example 1234.567 which means

$$1 \times 10^3 + 2 \times 10^2 + 3 \times 10^1 + 4 \times 10^0 + 5 \times 10^{-1} + 6 \times 10^{-2} + 7 \times 10^{-3}$$

More generally,

$$\dots d_j \dots d_1 d_0 . d_{-1} \dots d_{-i} \dots$$

Represents

$$\dots + d_j \times 10^j + \dots + d_0 \times 10^0 + d_{-1} \times 10^{-1} + \dots + d_{-i} \times 10^{-i} + \dots$$

In a computer only a finite subset of all numbers can be represented. These are the so-called floating-point numbers and they are

$$\bar{x} = (-1)^s \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} d_i \beta^{-i} \right) \beta^e$$

When ($s = 0,1$)

β is called the base

$\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} d_i \beta^{-i}$ is the significant or matissa, m is the mantissa length

e is the exponent

Machine precision

The machine precision, denoted by eps , is the smallest number, which satisfies

$$|x - rd(x)| \leq eps|x| \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

For all $x \in R$ within the range of the floating-point number system, where $rd(x)$ is rounding to the nearest machine number.

Note that, (1) is a relative error since for $x \in R \setminus \{0\}$ (within the range of the floating-point number system)

$$\frac{|x - rd(x)|}{|x|} \leq eps$$

5-digit Decimal Machine Number for π :

$$\pi = 0.314159265 \dots \times 10^1$$

$$\simeq 0.31415 \times 10^1 \text{ (Chopping)}$$

$$\simeq (0.31415 + 0.00001) \times 10^1 = 3.1416 \text{ (Rounding)}$$

Absolute errors:

$$|\pi - 3.1415| \approx 9 \times 10^{-5} \quad , \quad |\pi - 3.1416| \approx 7 \times 10^{-6}$$

Relative errors:

$$\frac{|\pi - 3.1415|}{\pi} \approx 3 \times 10^{-5} \quad , \quad \frac{|\pi - 3.1416|}{\pi} \approx 2 \times 10^{-6}$$

IEEE 754 Floating Point Standard:

The IEEE standard for floating point arithmetic (IEEE 754) is a technical standard for floating point computation which was established in 1985 by the IEEE. The exponent bias for single precision is 127, which means we must add the base 2 exponent to it. Double precision as perceived from the name is more precise and can hold larger numbers. Therefore, it's exponent bias is 1023.

Exponent bias = $2^{k-1} - 1$, where, k is the number of bits for exponent.

For a single-precision number, an exponent in the range $-126 \dots +127$ is biased by adding 127 to get a value in the range $1 \dots 254$ (0 and 255 have special meanings). For a double-precision number, an exponent in the range $-1022 \dots +1023$ is biased by adding 1023 to get a value in the range $1 \dots 2046$ (0 and 2047 have special meanings). [7]

Stability of an algorithm

The stability of an algorithm intuitively means that whether an algorithm performs well (stable) or badly (unstable) in significant cases. The stability can be determined on the basis of errors that arise in computations.

Chapter – 3

Iterative Methods for solving linear system

The general idea behind iterative methods is the following. Suppose we want to solve a linear system $Ax = b$, where A is an invertible square $n \times n$ matrix. If A is very large, say $n = 10^9$, then a direct solver as discussed in the previous chapter is no longer feasible for solving the linear system $Ax = b$ (since the number of elementary operations is $O(n^2)$). Instead, we want to use a so called iterative method which constructs a sequence $\{x^{(j)}\}$ of solutions in R^n that approximate the true solution x of $Ax = b$. For $j \rightarrow \infty$, we should have that

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} x^{(j)} = \hat{x}$$

Although in reality this will not always be the case, due to rounding errors and stability issues.

The most common form is

$$x^{(j+1)} = x^{(j)} + B^{-1}(b - Ax^{(j)}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where B is an invertible matrix such that B^{-1} is an approximation of the inverse A^{-1} . Usually, B will be a “simplified version” of A whose inverse can be easily computed.

To understand (1), replace B^{-1} by A^{-1} ; we obtain (multiplying from the left by A in the second step)

$$x^{(j+1)} = x^{(j)} + B^{-1}(b - Ax^{(j)}) \leftrightarrow Ax^{(j+1)} = Ax^{(j)} + b - Ax^{(j)} = b$$

That is, $x^{(j+1)}$ would then solve $Ax = b$. In (1), we have instead of A^{-1} , the approximation $x^{(j)}$ of $\hat{x}$, and the term

$$r^{(j)} = b - Ax^{(j)} = A(\hat{x} - x^{(j)})$$

is the residual of this approximation (which measures the discrepancy, mapped into the range of A , between $x^{(j)}$). We solve the equation

$$Ay = A(\hat{x} - x^{(j)}) = b - Ax^{(j)} = r^{(j)}$$

Approximately with the help of the approximation B^{-1} of A^{-1} , giving $y = \hat{x} - x^{(j)} \approx B^{-1}(b - Ax)$ and add this correction to the previous approximation; thus

$$x^{(j+1)} = x^{(j)} + B^{-1}(b - Ax^{(j)})$$

Sometimes it is not obvious that a complicated iterative method can be interpreted in this sense, but we will study some suitable iterative methods in this chapter.

- Fixed Point Iteration
- Successive Over Relaxation (SOR) Method
- Steepest-Descent Method
- Conjugate Gradient Method

Fixed Point Iteration

Fixed point:

Consider a function $F: C^n \rightarrow C^n$ or $(F: R^n \rightarrow R^n)$. A point $\hat{x} \in C^n$ or $(\hat{x} \in R^n)$ is called a fixed point of F , if $F(\hat{x}) = \hat{x}$

The equation $F(x) = x$ is also a fixed-point equation.

Let us write the matrix A for the linear system $Ax = b$ as $A = A - B + B$ with an invertible matrix B which can and will be chosen suitably. Then, the equation $Ax = b$ can be reformulated as

$$b = Ax = (A - B)x + Bx \leftrightarrow Bx = b - (A - B)x = (B - A)x + b$$

And hence as the fixed-point equation

$$x = B^{-1}(B - A)x + B^{-1}b := Cx + c$$

Where $C := B^{-1}(B - A)$ and $c := B^{-1}b$. Thus the solution x to $Ax = b$ is a fixed point of the mapping

$$F(x) = Cx + c$$

To calculate the fixed point, we can use the following simple iterative process. We first pick a starting point $x^{(0)}$ and then form

$$x^{(j+1)} := F(x^{(j)}), \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

SOR method

Successive Over Relaxation (SOR) Method, is a generalization of and improvement on the Gauss-Seidel Method for solving a system of linear equations $Ax = b$. SOR method was jointly developed by David M. Young and Stanley P. Frankel. It has faster convergence than Gauss-Jacobi and Gauss-Seidel iterative methods which can significantly reduce the computation (CPU) time

The SOR method was developed to accelerate the convergence of the Gauss-Seidel method. The idea is to successively form a weighted average between the previously computed value $x^{(k-1)}$ and the new value [5]

$$x_i^{(k)} = \frac{1}{a_{ii}} \left[b_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_{ij} x_j^{(k)} + \sum_{j=i+1}^n a_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right) \right], \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n.$$

weight the newly computed value by ω and the previous value by $(1 - \omega)$. By assuming that $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_{ij} x_j^{(k)}$ and $\sum_{j=i+1}^n a_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)}$ are ignored when $i=1$ and n , respectively, we have

$$x_i^{(k)} = \frac{\omega}{a_{ii}} \left[b_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_{ij} x_j^{(k)} + \sum_{j=i+1}^n a_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right) \right] + (1 - \omega)x_i^{(k-1)}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

For this method to provide an improvement over the Gauss-Seidel method, ω must be chosen carefully. It is called the relaxation parameter. If $\omega = 1$, the SOR method and the Gauss-Seidel method are identical. If $\omega > 1$, we are said to be using overrelaxation and if $\omega < 1$ we are using underrelaxation

$$x_i^{(k)} = \frac{\omega}{a_{ii}} \left[b_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_{ij} x_j^{(k)} + \sum_{j=i+1}^n a_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right) \right] + (1 - \omega)x_i^{(k-1)},$$

$$i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

It has been seen that poor choice of the relaxation parameter ω can lead to poor convergence rates. On the other hand, a good choice of ω can lead to very fast convergence compared to the Jacobi or Gauss-Seidel methods. The spectral radius of B_{SOR} is the eigenvalue of B_{SOR} with maximum magnitude, and we want to choose ω so that $|\rho B_{SOR}(\omega)|$ is a minimum. Finding the optimal value of ω is very difficult in general, and the optimal value is known only for special types of matrices. It is known, however, that ω must satisfy $0 < \omega < 2$.

Necessary and Sufficient Condition for the convergence of SOR Method

If A is a Hermitian (symmetric) positive definite matrix and $0 < \omega < 2$, the *SOR* iterations converge for any choice of $x^{(0)}$

Steepest-Descent Method for solving the system $Ax = b$

Steepest Descent (SD) is an elegant iterative method for solving large systems of linear equations. SD is effective for systems

$$Ax = b$$

Where x is an unknown vector b is a known vector, and A is known, $n \times n$ square, symmetric, positive-definite matrix.

The scalar product of two vectors is written $x^T y$, and represents the following sum:

$$x^T y = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i$$

Steepest-Descent Method: The steepest descent method was first published by Peter Debye in 1909

We eager to solve the following large systems of linear equations using Steepest Descent method

$$Ax = b$$

where x is an unknown vector, b is a known vector, and is a known, $n \times n$ square, symmetric, positive-definite matrix. We then consider a quadratic form of the vector x of the following form

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} x^T A x - b^T x$$

In the method of steepest, we start at an arbitrary point $x^{(0)}$ and slide down to the bottom of the paraboloid. We take a series of steps $x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots$ until we are satisfied the we are close enough to the solution x

When we take a step, we choose the direction in which f decreases most quickly, which is the direction opposite $f'(x^{(i)})$. According to the system $Ax = b$,

We find $-f'(x^{(i)}) = b - Ax^{(i)}$.

The residual $r^{(i)} = b - Ax^{(i)}$ indicates how far we are from the correct value of b . It is easy to see that $r^{(i)} = Ax - Ax^{(i)} = -A(x^{(i)} - x) = -Ae^{(i)}$, where $e^i = x^{(i)} - x$. The residual can be treated as the error transformed by A into the same space as b . More importantly

$$r^{(i)} = -f'(x^{(i)})$$

The residual can be considered as the direction of steepest descent (whenever we read “residual”, think “direction of steepest descent”). Suppose we start at $x^{(0)}$. Our first step, along the direction of steepest descent. In other words, we will choose a point

$$x^{(1)} = x^{(0)} + ar^{(0)}$$

A line search is a procedure that chooses α to minimize f along a line $x^{(1)} = x^{(0)} + ar^{(0)}$. α minimizes f when the derivative $\frac{d}{d\alpha} f(x^{(1)})$ is equal to zero. By the chain rule,

$$\frac{d}{d\alpha} f(x^{(1)}) = \frac{df(x^{(1)})}{dx^{(1)}} \frac{dx^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = -f'(x^{(i)})r^{(0)}$$

Since, the Steepest Descent method approaches the minimum, where the new search direction is orthogonal to the previous. To determine α , we note that $-f'(x^{(i)}) = -r^{(i)}$, and we have

$$(r^{(1)})^T r^{(0)} = 0 \Rightarrow (b - Ax^{(1)})^T r^{(0)} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (b - A(x^{(0)} + ar^{(0)}))^T r^{(0)} = 0$$

$$\alpha = \frac{(r^{(0)})^T r^{(0)}}{(r^{(0)})^T Ar^{(0)}}$$

Putting it all together, the method of Steepest Descent is [6]

$$r^{(i)} = b - Ax^{(i)}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{(r^{(0)})^T r^{(0)}}{(r^{(0)})^T Ar^{(0)}}$$

$$x^{(i+1)} = x^{(i)} + \alpha_i r^{(i)}$$

for $i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Conjugate Gradient Method for solving the system

$$Ax = b$$

The conjugate gradient method is an algorithm to solve a particular system of linear equations, namely those whose matrix is symmetric and positive definite. The conjugate gradient method is often implemented as an iterative method, applicable to sparse systems that are too large to be handled by a direct implementation or other direct methods. It was mainly developed by Magnus Hestenes and Eduard Stiefel.

Conjugate-gradient method uses so-called A-conjugate search directions instead of orthogonal search directions.

We eager to solve the following large systems of linear equations using Conjugate Gradient method

$$Ax = b$$

where x is an unknown vector, b is a known vector, and A is a known, $n \times n$ square, symmetric, positive-definite matrix. We then consider a quadratic form of the vector x of the following form [7]

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} x^T A x - b^T x$$

In the method of steepest, we start at an arbitrary point $x^{(0)}$ and slide down to the bottom of the paraboloid. We take a series of steps $x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots$ until we are satisfied that we are close enough to the solution x

We recall that the Gram-Schmidt process takes a set of linearly independent vectors and produces a set of mutually orthogonal unit vectors relative to the 2-norm that span the same subspace as the original set. To find $\{p_i\}$, we apply the Gram-Schmidt process to the residual vectors $\{r_i\}$ but using the energy inner product and norm. Start with $r^{(0)} = b - Ax_0$. The set of vectors $\{p_i\}$ must be A-conjugate ($P_i^T A P_j = 0, i \neq j$) but it is not necessary that they be unit vectors. If we skip the normalization step of Gram-Schmidt at step i we have

$$P_i = r_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} C_{j,i} P_j$$

$$\text{where } C_{ji} = \frac{r_i^T A P_j}{P_i^T A P_j}$$

The purpose of the Equation is to determine the next search direction from the current residual and the previous search directions.

We take the inner product of P_j and $r_i, j < i$

$$r_i^T P_j = r_i^T r_j - \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} C_{kj} r_i^T P_k = r_i^T r_j = 0$$

And all the residuals are orthogonal to the previous ones. Similarly,

$$\langle P_i, r_i \rangle = \|r_i\|_2^2 - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} C_{ji} \langle r_i, P_j \rangle = \|r_i\|_2^2$$

Finally, we obtain,

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\|r_i\|_2^2}{\langle AP_i, P_i \rangle}$$

Chapter – 4

Numerical Methods for computing Eigenvalues

Eigenvalue Problem

For a squared matrix $A \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, the problem that consists in finding the solutions $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$

and nonzero $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ of the algebraic equation

$$A\mathbf{x} = \lambda\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

is called an eigenvalue problem. The scalar λ is called an “eigenvalue,” and the vector

$\mathbf{x}$ is an “eigenvector.” If we consider real matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, we can also study the eigenvalue problem (1), but the eigenvalue λ and eigenvector $\mathbf{x}$ may not be real and, in full generality, can belong to $\mathbb{C}$ or $\mathbb{C}^n$ respectively.

Some well-known numerical methods for computing eigenvalues of a large matrix are as follows:

- Singla value Decomposition
- Power Method
- Jacobi Method

Singular Value Decomposition

If A is an $m \times n$ matrix, then $A^T A$ is an $n \times n$ symmetric matrix with nonnegative eigenvalues. The singular values of an $m \times n$ matrix are the square roots of the eigenvalues of $A^T A$, and the 2-norm of a matrix is the largest singular value. The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) factors A into a product of two orthogonal matrices and a diagonal matrix of its singular values.

Algorithm of the Singular Value Decomposition

Let $A \in R^{m \times n}$ be a matrix. We eager to compute the SVD of the matrix A using the following algorithm.

Step 1: Compute the transpose of A , A^T and $A^T A$

Step 2: Determine the eigenvalues of $A^T A$ and sort these in descending order, in the absolute sense. Square roots these to obtain the singular values of A

Step 3: Construct diagonal matrix $\bar{\Sigma}$ by placing singular values in descending order along its diagonal. Compute its inverse, $\bar{\Sigma}^{-1}$

Step 4: Use the ordered eigenvalues from step 2 and compute the eigenvectors of $A^T A$. Place these eigenvectors along the columns of V and compute its transpose, V^T .

Step 5: Compute U as $U = A V \bar{\Sigma}^{-1}$. To complete the process, compute the full SVD using $A = U \bar{\Sigma} V^T$

Power Method

The power method was developed by Richard von Mises as it is also known as the Von Mises iteration.

Let $A \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ be a square matrix. A non-zero vector $x \in \mathbb{C}^n$ is an eigenvector of A and $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ is its corresponding eigenvalue if $Ax = \lambda x$.

The eigenvalues are the roots of the characteristic polynomial

$$\rho(A, \lambda) = \det(\lambda I - A)$$

However, for larger matrices it is not practicable to actually compute the characteristic polynomial, let alone its roots. Hence, we will look at more feasible methods to numerically determine eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

The simplest method to compute eigenvalues and eigenvectors of a matrix is the power method. In practice, this method is confined to the computation of some (not all) extreme eigenvalues, provided that they are real and simple (their algebraic multiplicity is equal to 1) Suppose λ_1 , has a dominant eigenvalue $|\lambda_1| > |\lambda_2| \geq |\lambda_3| \dots \geq |\lambda_n|$. For such matrices, it is now our goal to determine the dominant eigenvalue λ_1 and a corresponding eigenvector.

Let $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, and assume that A has n real eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_n \in \mathbb{R}$ (counted with multiplicity) and a corresponding set of real normalized eigenvectors *that is* $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$ that form a basis of

. (That is, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_n$ are linearly independent, and $\|w_j\|_2 = 1$ and $Aw_j = \lambda_j w_j$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.) Suppose that A has a dominant eigenvalue λ_1 , that is, $|\lambda_1| > |\lambda_j|$ for $j = 2, 3, \dots, n$. The power method or von Mises iteration is defined in the following way: First, we choose a starting vector

$$x^{(0)} = \sum_{j=1}^n c_j w_j \text{ with } c_1 \neq 0$$

And set

$y^{(0)} = \frac{x^{(0)}}{\|x^{(0)}\|_2}$ then for $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ we compute :

$$1. x^{(m)} = Ay^{(m-1)}$$

$$2. y^{(m)} = \sigma_m \frac{x^{(m)}}{\|x^{(m)}\|_2}$$

Where the sign $\sigma_m \in \{1, -1\}$ is chosen such that $y^{(m)T} y^{(m-1)} \geq 0$

Chapter – 5

Numerical Methods for Solving ODEs

Since we have no hope of solving the vast majority of differential equations in explicit, analytic form, the design of suitable numerical algorithms for accurately approximating solutions is essential. The ubiquity of differential equations throughout mathematics and its applications has driven the tremendous research effort devoted to numerical solution schemes, some dating back to the beginnings of the calculus. Explicit solutions, when known, can also be used as test cases for tracking the reliability and accuracy of a chosen numerical scheme

An ordinary differential equation (ODE) is an equation for a function $u(t)$, defined on an interval $I \subset \mathbb{R}$ and with values in the real or complex numbers or in the space $\mathbb{R}^d$ ($\mathbb{C}^d$), of the form

$$F(t, u, u'(t), u''(t), \dots, u^n(t)) = 0$$

Here, $F(\dots)$ denotes an arbitrary function of its arguments. The order n of a differential equation is the highest derivative which occurs. If the dimension d of the value range of u is higher than one, we talk about systems of differential equations.

Numerical Methods for IVPs

Numerical solution to IVPs refers to finding an approximation by applying a discretization method, and subsequently. We consider the following problem: given an IVP of the form

$$\begin{cases} u'(t) = f(t, u(t)), & 0 \leq t \leq T \\ u(t_0) = u_0, \end{cases}$$

calculate the value $u(t)$ at a later point in time T . To do so, we insert intermediate points and apply the method to each subinterval, where we use the result of a previous interval as the initial point for the next subinterval.

Since there are infinitely many values between 0 and T , we will only be concerned here to find approximations of the solution. Divide $[0, T]$ into n equal subintervals of length $h = \frac{b-a}{n}$. On a time, interval $I = [0, T]$, we define a partitioning in n subintervals, also known as time steps. Here we choose the following notation:

The time steps $I_k = [t_{k-1}, t_k]$ have the step size $h_k = t_k - t_{k-1}$. A partitioning in n time steps $t_n = T$. The term k -th time step is used for both the interval, and for the point in time t_k , but it should always be clear through context which one is meant. Very often, we will consider evenly spaced time steps, in which case we denote the step size by h and $h_k = h$ for all k .

There are different types of numerical methods for solving IVPs, such as

1. Single step method
2. Multistep method, etc.

Single step method for solving IVPs

An explicit single-step (one-step) method is a method which, given u_0 at $t_0 = 0$ computes a sequence of approximations $u_1, \dots, u_n$ to the solution of an IVP in the time steps $t_1, \dots, t_n$ using an update formula of the form

$$u_k = u_{k-1} + h_k F(t_{k-1}, u_{k-1})$$

The function $F(\dots)$ is called increment function. The method is called single-step method because the value u_k , explicitly depends only of the values u_{k-1} and $f(t_{k-1}, u_{k-1})$, not on previous values.

There are several types of single step method.

- 1) Euler's Method
- 2) Runge-kutta method

Multistep methods for solving IVPs

Multistep methods for solving IVPs use information at more than one previous point to estimate solution at next grid point. Multistep methods are characterized by using solution approximations earlier than y_n in the update formula for advancing the numerical approximation from y_n to y_{n+1} . This is in contrast with one-step methods, which use only y_n besides possibly additional intermediate (e.g. stage) quantities.

There are several multistep methods for solving IVPs, among them, the most common multistep methods are

1. Adams-Bashforth Method
2. Adams-Moulton Method (Predictor-Corrector Method)

Chapter – 6

Machine learning

Correlation between machine learning and mathematics

Machine learning is all about mathematics, which aids in the development of an algorithm capable of learning from data and making an accurate forecast. The prediction may be as basic as identifying dogs or cats from a given set of images, or it could be as complex as recommending items to a consumer based on previous purchases. As a result, it is critical to fully comprehend the mathematical ideas behind any fundamental machine learning algorithm. In this manner, it assists anyone in selecting all of the appropriate algorithms for your machine learning project.

Linear Algebra Concept in Machine Learning

Linear Algebra concept plays a vital role in machine learning. For instance, linear algebra is a fundamental component in developing central machine learning algorithms. Basically, linear algebra is a must to evaluate and observe data collections. Linear algebra is applied in machine learning algorithms in loss functions, regularization, covariance matrices, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), Matrix Operations, and support vector machine classification. It is also applied in machine learning algorithms like linear regression. These are the concepts that are needed for understanding the optimization methods used for machine learning. [8]

Application of Numerical methods in Machine learning

Learning/Parameter Estimation

A learning machine's purpose is frequently stated in terms of an optimization problem, i.e., the minimization or maximizing of a mathematical function.

When an analytical solution to the optimization problem does not exist, numerical approaches are essential.

The most widely used numerical optimization algorithms in machine learning (ML) make use of derivative information (for example, gradient descent, accelerated gradient descent techniques such as Momentum, Nestorov, and others, Newton's method, and L-BFGS).

Stochastic approximation methods (for example, stochastic gradient descent) are also popular and have grown in importance as enormous datasets have proliferated.

The Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm and its variations are prominent numerical approaches for estimating hidden/latent variables in models (for example, Gaussian mixture model, Hidden Markov Random Field, Structural Equation Model with latent variables).

These algorithms are commonly used in regression models (for example, neural network models with real valued output, large scale linear regression models), classification models (for example, logistic regression and multinomial regression), clustering models (for example, k-means clustering, Gaussian mixture model), structure learning models (for example, Hidden Markov Model, Conditional Random Field), and reinforcement learning models.

Inference

Inference in huge probability distributions, such as Markov Random Fields (a Boltzmann Machine is a specific form of an MRF), is frequently intractable due to the computationally intractable normalization constant. As a result, answering questions like "what is the most likely value under this distribution?" necessitates the use of numerical methods like Monte Carlo Markov Chain methods (for example, Metropolis Hastings algorithm, Metropolis algorithm, Gibbs sampler) that can yield approximations. For model evaluation, cross-validation type algorithms are commonly used.

Numerical approaches, such as bootstrapping, are frequently used to supplement parametric methods for hypothesis testing.

Numerical Integration

Large integrals (or sums) are a common operation in ML. Bayesian statistics, for example, frequently necessitates the computation of extremely large multidimensional integrals.

Another typical process in ML is the computation of expectancies, which frequently necessitates the computation of huge integrals (examples include EM type algorithms, MRF learning algorithms). In these instances, numerical approaches such as Monte Carlo methods are frequently used.

Numerical Linear Algebra

Matrix operations such as matrix inversion, finding eigenvalues, and matrix factorization are critical in all areas of ML and necessitate numerical computing. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and related approaches such as Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA), and

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), for example, all need numerically computing a matrix's Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) (or Generalized SVD).

Algorithm stability and performance are dependent on underlying numerical linear algebra routines (among other things), hence smart practitioners will ensure that their preferred language/ML package incorporates optimized linear algebra libraries (for example, LAPACK).

Finite Precision Arithmetic

Because the digital computer restricts our computations to finite precision arithmetic, it is critical to build algorithms that defend against frequent concerns caused by this constraint, such as rounding mistakes resulting in overflow or underflow. A excellent case in point is the implementation of the SoftMax function, which is extensively used in machine learning. [9]

Conclusion

Numerical Analysis being a crucial part of any engineering problems. Solution of any problem should be less time consuming and have to be accurate. For any problem, we have to check which method works best for that certain problem. To establish a numerical method, there is a certain convergence rules and the solution method has to be stable too. To find the solution of the growing machine learning problems, numerical analysis is one of the best way to go closer to the answer without knowing anything regarding solution.

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